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URENIO Research, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki

URENIO Research Working Papers

#25.01

March 2025

A conceptual synthesis of 25 years of regional development research: Core thematic communities and emerging frontiers

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Abstract

Regional development is an intricate process that involves various components and actors interacting within complex, evolving environments. Despite numerous studies on specific aspects of the field, a comprehensive overview of the intellectual structure has remained underexplored. This fragmentation limits the ability to grasp broader trends and interconnections shaping regional development research. To address this gap, this study utilizes a bibliometric analysis to examine the intellectual structure of regional development over the past 25 years. Drawing from initially 15,226 source documents extracted from Scopus, the study constructs a document citation network including 15,488 co-citations (edges) among 7,882 source documents (nodes). Citation relationships among these publications are analyzed using weighted in-degree calculations in Gephi, while the Louvain modularity algorithm identifies research communities based on shared themes. Additionally, topic modeling techniques in R, utilizing word frequency and co-occurrence analysis, uncovering dominant thematic areas within the field. Key findings reveal the interconnectedness of various research communities, with a particular emphasis on path dependence and industrial evolution, the role of Higher Education Institutions, regional disparities and inequality, entrepreneurial ecosystems, EU Cohesion Policy, the rise of the city-regions, tourism and globalized regional development. This study provides a comprehensive framework for understanding the intellectual landscape of regional development, offering valuable insights for researchers, policymakers, and practitioners aiming to navigate this complex and evolving field.

Keywords: regional development, bibliometric analysis, text mining, topic modelling

JEL Codes: R11, R58, O18

1. Introduction

Regional development is a complex process involving a diverse range of components and actors that interact not only with one another but also with their broader environment. Systematically exploring the knowledge produced in this field requires a comprehensive approach due to its inherently multidisciplinary nature. While numerous studies have attempted to conceptualize various aspects of regional development, most focus on specific elements of this broad domain, such as theoretical frameworks (Zhu et al., 2019; Janik et al., 2020; Drago et al., 2023), planning strategies (Sharifi et al., 2023; Veckalne & Tambovceva, 2023), or entrepreneurial activities (Baumgartner et al., 2013; Dan & Goia, 2018). This fragmented approach does not allow us to gain a wide overview of the knowledge being produced in the field of regional development, making it more targeted and biased.

Previous studies in the field, despite being more targeted, have identified key elements that shape

research on regional development. Concepts such as "path dependence," "innovation systems," "inequality," "universities," and "rural development" have emerged as core research areas over the past two decades (Ryser & Halseth, 2010; Zhu et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2021; Veckalne & Tambovceva, 2023). Additionally, there has been a notable increase in publications focusing on China's regional development patterns (Zhang et al., 2021), reflecting the country's growing influence on global economic and spatial dynamics.

The aim of this study is to provide a comprehensive understanding of the knowledge being produced in the field of regional development without restricting the focus to specific subfields. This open-ended approach offers a unique opportunity to identify overarching themes, emerging trends, and interdisciplinary connections, ultimately contributing to a more holistic view of how regional development is conceptualized and studied. By adopting this broad perspective, the study seeks to bridge gaps between fragmented research areas and facilitate a deeper understanding of the complex factors driving regional growth and transformation.

To achieve this, the study employs bibliometric analysis to examine the intellectual structure of regional development research over the past 25 years. Using 15,226 source documents extracted from Scopus, a rigorous data cleansing process removed inadequate records, resulting in a final dataset of 14,083 publications, including journal articles, books, conference papers, and reviews. A document citation network was constructed by analyzing citation relationships among these publications, identifying key research themes and influential works through weighted in-degree calculations in Gephi. The network's structure was further explored using the Louvain modularity algorithm to detect research communities based on shared interests. Additionally, topic modeling techniques in R were applied to abstracts, leveraging word frequency and co-occurrence analysis to identify the 8 core thematic communities, which are then being described in detail.

A synthesis of this exercise is performed as the final step of this process, aimed at developing a framework for understanding the key elements of regional development research and their interactions. This framework seeks to systematically conceptualize the knowledge being produced and, rather than merely offering a descriptive output, to operationalize the insights derived from this bibliometric analysis. This added value benefits researchers, policymakers, and practitioners by enabling them to better position their understanding of the field. Furthermore, it facilitates more informed decision-making, supports strategic research planning, and fosters interdisciplinary collaboration by highlighting key thematic areas and influential contributions within regional development research.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 outlines the methodology used in this bibliometric study, detailing the process of constructing the document citation network and applying text mining techniques for topic modeling and content analysis. It also covers the data processing and cleansing steps. Section 3 provides an in-depth overview of the identified research communities, highlighting the main research topics and emerging areas for each. Section 4 presents a comprehensive discussion of the findings and their connection to the proposed framework. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper by summarizing the key insights and contributions for researchers and policymakers, along with addressing limitations and suggesting avenues for future research.

2. Research methodology

The intellectual structure of a research field can be envisioned as a mosaic, with individual scientific publications acting as its foundational elements. These publications, united by shared conceptual themes, coalesce into larger research communities that collectively define and shape the broader scientific

landscape. Bibliometric analysis offers a tool to analyze the intellectual structure of a research field, revealing connections between the identified scientific publications (De Bellis, 2009; Small and Griffith, 1974), which are usually referred to as source documents (Casillas and Acedo, 2007; Mora et al., 2017).

This bibliometric study was carried out by using 15,226 source documents, which represent all the publications relating to the field of regional development over the last 25 years period. The source documents were extracted from Scopus, by means of a keyword search aiming at identifying all the academic literature related to regional development published between 2000 and 2024. The source literature was found by running the following search query: TITLE-ABS-KEY (“regional development”)¹. Our final dataset of source documents includes journal articles, books, book chapters, conference papers, and reviews. A breakdown of the source documents by type is presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Breakdown of the initial source documents derived from Scopus by type. Note: Ar – Article; Bo – Book; Ch – Book Chapter; Co – Conference paper; Re – Review.

During the data cleansing process, we checked for errors in the extracted dataset (Adam, 2002). A manual check was performed to identify any mistakes in the data collected or the presence of inadequate records, i.e. records that were duplicates or were missing essential information. After performing the manual check, 1,143 of the initial records (7.5% of the total) were considered inadequate, and therefore excluded from the sample. The final sample included 14,083 source documents. For each source document the following information was extracted: publication title; authors and affiliations; year of publication; keywords; document type; abstract; and cited references, which were necessary to undertake the document citation network analysis.

To build the document citation network, citation data was extracted from the identified 14,083 source documents using the tm library in R programming language. This analysis includes only regional development-related intellectual works that have either cited or have been cited by other publications within the regional development field. This methodological approach uses citations as both a measure of similarity and a means of linking publications with shared cognitive interests (Fitzpatrick et al., 2018).

¹ To limit the large number of publications obtained for this period and keep the focus on the regional dimension, we limited our search in the fields of Social Sciences; Environmental Science; Economic, Econometrics and Finance; Business, Management and Accounting; Engineering; Energy; Computer Science; Agricultural and Biological Science; and Arts and Humanities.

It highlights that the central topics and core research themes of a field are anchored in its highly cited publications and the network of subsequent works that build upon their content (Panori et al., 2019; Mora et al., 2020). The document co-citation extraction process identified 15,488 co-citations (edges) among 7,882 source documents (nodes), representing 55.96% of the initial source document dataset (14,083). This subset was then used to construct the document citation network in the open-source software Gephi.

The identification of the most influential source documents in our network was based on the weighted in-degree of each node, as it has been calculated in Gephi. This measure is based on the number of inbound links held by each node, determining its influence on the overall network. The source documents with the highest weighted in-degree were identified as the core contributors to knowledge production within the network.

Following Panori et al. (2019), the document citation network, including 15,488 co-citations (edges) among 7,882 source documents (nodes), was analyzed in Gephi to explore the intellectual exchange among the identified source documents, forming communities with shared research interests. Identifying these communities involves clustering the network data, where each node is assigned to a specific cluster. This process can be carried out using either spectral clustering techniques or network modularity optimization methods (Porter et al., 2009; Fortunato, 2010). Among these approaches, network modularity optimization has demonstrated greater effectiveness for detecting communities in large-scale networks (De Meo et al., 2011) and was therefore chosen to investigate the community structure within the derived author citation network. Specifically, the Louvain modularity algorithm developed by Blondel et al. (2008)—the most widely used method for such analyses (Glänzel and Thijs, 2017; Yu et al., 2017)—was employed to assess the strength of the division within the large network of publications, organizing them into clusters of thematically related items.

Finally, topic modelling using text mining techniques in the R programming language were applied to the abstracts of the source documents to uncover the key thematic areas represented by the primary communities within the document citation network. Word frequency and co-occurrence were used as the main indicators for this topic identification process. The *tm* and *quanteda* packages in R were used for calculating word frequency and co-occurrence between terms in each research community (Benoit et al., 2017). Log-likelihood has been chosen as the key measure to check the significance of co-occurrence between terms (Niekler et al., 2014).

Even though the identified methodological approach was suitable for the key premises of this bibliometric analysis, it is important to acknowledge and justify any potential limitations related to it. First, using a single database to gather source documents may have missed relevant academic publications on regional development, as different databases retrieve varying sets of publications depending on the subject (Ball and Tunger, 2006; Bar-Ilan, 2018). To address this, Scopus and Web of Science were tested, and Scopus was found to offer broader coverage, retrieving 2,422 additional titles. Second, the exclusion of Google Scholar from the data collection phase was due to its limited search and filtering features, lack of export capabilities, and absence of quality control mechanisms (Haddaway et al., 2015; Halevi et al., 2017), which led to the omission of grey literature from the study.

Fig. 2 provides a schematic representation of the overall document citation network, illustrating the structure of the regional development knowledge field in terms of its key thematic areas over the past 25 years (2000-2024). The network consists of nodes and edges, where nodes represent source documents and edges indicate identified citations. The diameter of each node is proportional to its in-degree centrality, meaning that publications with a higher number of citations are depicted with larger

node diameters in the graph.

Fig. 2. Document citation network and thematic communities. Source: Author’s elaboration.

The analysis of the document citation network identified 8 core research communities of thematically related publications, consisting of 3,291 source documents. These documents account for 41.75% of the network's nodes and contribute to 59.10% of the total in-degree. The remaining nodes in the network lacked sufficient connections to form distinct thematic communities. Table 1 presents the core characteristics of each community, listing the number of source documents, its network and in-degree share and the most frequent word collocation based on their abstracts. A detailed table presenting the top 10 source documents with their specific characteristics, including title, authors, year of publication, type, and in-degree centrality as derived by the document citation network is given in Appendix (Table A.1).

Table 1: Thematic communities’ overview.

Thematic Community	Title	No./Share of Source documents	Share of total In-degree	Most frequent word collocation
C1	Path	573/7.27%	17.11%	path development / path creation / new path

	dependence and industrial evolution			- 169 regional innovation - 166 smart specialization - 165 innovation system(s) - 110 innovation policy / policies - 98 peripheral regions - 42 related variety - 32 economic resilience - 32 knowledge base - 27 entrepreneurial discovery - 25 higher education - 156 regional innovation - 114 education institutions / regional universities - 90 innovation system(s) - 87 technology transfer - 40 knowledge transfer - 39 universities role - 38 human capital - 35 triple helix - 33 regional inequality / regional disparities - 136 China's regional development / River Delta - 82 land use / land development - 66 human capital - 63 socio-economic development / economic social - 52 developing countries - 30 development policies - 29 social capital - 28 regional innovation - 27 entrepreneurial ecosystem(s) - 157 business formation / firm formation / new business / new firm -130
C2	The role of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs)	505/6.41%	8.27%	social capital - 47 entrepreneurial activity - 39 regional innovation - 36 regional policy - 28 local development - 25 European Union / Member States / EU regions - 199 Cohesion policy / regional policy - 185 Structural funds / Development funds / EU
C3	Regional disparities and inequality	486/6.17%	7.81%	
C4	Entrepreneurial ecosystems	452/5.73%	7.68%	
C5	EU Cohesion Policy	342/4.34%	5.46%	

				funds - 130
				European regional / EU regional - 72
				EU cohesion - 39
				Development policy - 33
				Regional disparities - 28
				urban agglomeration(s) / urban network / metropolitan areas - 123
				Yangtze River Delta / Hong Kong / Pearl River Delta / Northeast China - 121
				land use / land finance / land supply / land development / urban land - 118
C6	Rise of the city-regions	326/4.14%	3.58%	carbon emission(s) / CO2 emissions - 90
				urban shrinkage / shrinking cities / city shrinkage - 78
				regional integration - 48
				urban development / urban growth - 44
				coordinated development - 42
				tourism development - 106
				nature-based tourism / national park(s) / protected areas - 89
				rural areas / rural tourism / rural development - 67
				tourism sector / tourism industry / tourism research - 61
C7	Tourism	312/3.96%	3.22%	regional tourism - 55
				wine tourism - 49
				local food / food tourism - 48
				regional governance / policy makers / regional policy - 38
				sustainable tourism - 24
				global production network(s) - 51
				foreign direct investment - 24
C8	Globalized regional development	295/3.74%	5.97%	Yangtze river delta / Pearl River delta - 24
				regional development agencies - 10
				regional development policy / policies - 17

Source: Author's elaboration.

Fig. 3 offers an overview of the temporal evolution of the share of source document publications within each community, providing insights into their distribution over the study period. Notably, thematic communities C1, C3, C5 and C6 experienced a significant increase between 2020 and 2024. These include aspects related to industrial evolution, regional disparities, the effects of EU Cohesion Policy on regional development, and the dynamic relationship between the rise of urban agglomerations and regional development. On the contrary, thematic areas related to the role of HEIs (C2), entrepreneurial ecosystems (C4), tourism (C7) and globalized regional development (C8), have remained relatively stable over the past decade.

Fig. 3. Temporal evolution of the share of source document publications within each community.
Source: Author's elaboration.

3. Research communities

The following sub-sections offer an overview of each of the identified communities based on the top source documents according to their network in-degree, trying to capture their key focus and semantic structure. Additionally, emerging areas of interest have been identified for some of the rapidly developed communities based on the most frequent word collocations observed in source documents from the last two years of research.

3.1 Community 1: Path dependence and industrial evolution

The first research community focuses on key concepts related to the development and transformation of regional economies, particularly through industrial restructuring and innovation processes. Central to the community's themes are the notions of path development, path creation, and new paths, which highlight how regions can build or shift their economic trajectories (Martin & Sunley, 2006; Frenken et al., 2007; Neffke et al., 2011). These terms have been developed under the paradigm of evolutionary economic geography (EEG) trying to investigate the ways in which new paths unfold in space and over time (Hassink et al., 2019). A significant focus is placed on peripheral regions, which face unique challenges but also opportunities for growth, often through the harnessing of related variety, where industries or sectors with complementary knowledge bases support one another's development (Frenken et al., 2007; Dawley, 2014; Isaksen, 2014; Isaksen & Tripl, 2017).

The community also explores the broader concept of innovation systems, examining how various actors (firms, universities, and government institutions) interact within regional contexts to drive technological advancements and economic growth (Dawley, 2014; Hassink et al., 2019). A key focus is placed on the dynamic and interdependent nature of these relationships, emphasizing that innovation does not occur in isolation but rather emerges from complex networks of collaboration, knowledge exchange, and institutional support (Hassink, 2005). In this context, industrial evolution is not a linear process, but a multi-actor construction shaped by both deliberate strategic actions and broader structural changes (Grillitsch & Sotarauta, 2020). Actors not only contribute to the formation of new industrial

trajectories but also leverage emerging opportunities to enhance their own competitiveness.

Innovation policy plays a critical role in shaping these dynamics, guiding the development of strategies and frameworks for innovation at regional and national levels. The idea of regional innovation is strongly emphasized, often in the context of smart specialization, a policy approach encouraging regions to focus on their unique strengths for growth and innovation (Foray, 2014; Balland et al., 2019). The knowledge base is a key component of this community, emphasizing how regions leverage existing capabilities to fuel further innovation. Finally, the concept of entrepreneurial discovery emerges as a process where entrepreneurs identify new opportunities for growth, often driven by the dynamic interaction between knowledge, resources, and innovation policy.

Emerging areas of interest in this research community relate to the idea of system-level agency, social innovation, and regional development traps. In the first case, system-level agency refers to activities performed by regional stakeholders towards altering the functioning and supporting elements of regional innovation structures for enabling new path creation (Uyarra & Flanagan, 2022; Blažek & Květoň, 2023; Blažek et al., 2024). Second, new evidence suggests that social innovation may act as a counterbalance for promoting a more sustainable regional innovation policy, especially in less developed regions where community ties are much stronger resulting in higher endogenous potential (Meyer, 2022; Herzog & Krehl, 2024). A specific focus has been placed in rural areas where social innovation may act as a key element for promoting transformative changes (Castro-Arce & Vanclay, 2020; Suitner et al., 2023). Finally, the discussion on development traps has intensified, focusing on how certain regions become locked into low-growth equilibria due to structural constraints, institutional weaknesses, and limited adaptive capacity. Studies highlight that escaping such traps requires a combination of bottom-up initiatives, institutional restructuring, and strategic interventions that enhance innovation capabilities (Diemer et al., 2022; Rodríguez-Pose et al., 2024; Roessler, 2024).

3.2 Community 2: The role of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs)

The second research community examines how Higher Education Institutions, such as universities, contribute to the economic, social, and technological advancement of regions (Boucher et al., 2003). More specifically, research in this area highlights that HEIs serve as hubs for human capital development and knowledge transfer, empowering skills and disseminating research findings to local industries and communities (Goldstein & Renault, 2004; Charles, 2006). This process is fundamental for promoting the idea of knowledge-based economic development, which is essential not only for attracting and retaining industries that rely on specialized knowledge and competencies, but also for creating competitive advantages for regions (Cooke & Leydesdorff, 2006).

Moreover, through technology transfer initiatives, universities enable the commercialization of research outputs, leading to the development of new products and services that stimulate regional economic growth (Harrison & Leitch, 2010). Differences arise between developed and less developed regions in terms of their ability to leverage the benefits of knowledge production within their regional economic structures, indicating that universities located in more competitive regions show higher impact in their ability for efficient technology transfer to local businesses (Huggins & Johnston, 2009).

The concept of regional innovation systems is central to this discourse, where HEIs act as pivotal actors for promoting the idea of the learning region (Charles, 2003; Caniëls & Van den Bosch, 2011; Trippel et al., 2015). Evidence suggests that the extent to which HEIs can strengthen regional innovation systems depends on several aspects, such as their specific characteristics, the type of the existing regional firms, the collaborative relationship between the local actors, as well as the institutional context

under which they operate and are embedded (Asheim et al., 2011; Caniëls & Van den Bosch, 2011).

In terms of policy development, the Triple Helix model, which describes the interaction between universities, industry, and government, is often employed to understand the collaborative dynamics that underpin successful regional innovation ecosystems (Etzkowitz & Klofsten, 2005; Caniëls & Van den Bosch, 2011). In this framework, HEIs not only contribute to technological advancements but also play a role in shaping policies and strategies that align with regional development goals, depending on the role that each regional government aims at providing them (Trippel et al., 2015). Therefore, potential transformations in university-industry-government relations should be considered in each case for achieving the desired contextual regional organization of the local actors (Cooke & Leydesdorff, 2006).

3.3 Community 3: Regional disparities and inequality

This study identifies a third community of research that explores both existing and emerging patterns of regional inequality. A central focus of this literature is the persistence of regional disparities in both developed and developing economies, with particular emphasis on China's regional development. Scholars in this field argue that regional inequality arises from a complex interplay of factors, including land use, human and social capital, regional policies, and economic structures (Fleisher et al., 2010; Wei, 2015; Storper, 2021).

A key theoretical foundation for understanding these disparities is the New Economic Geography framework, particularly Krugman's (1991) core-periphery model, which explains the spatial concentration of economic activities. Although this model has faced criticism for its limited applicability to advanced economies, it remains highly relevant in analyzing regional specialization and economic integration in developing contexts such as China (Krugman, 2011).

Research on China, which constitutes a significant portion of this scholarly community, highlights stark economic differences between coastal and interior regions. Coastal areas such as the Pearl River Delta and the Yangtze Delta experience faster growth due to their strategic locations, superior infrastructure, and integration into global markets (Wei, 2007). Studies indicate that while infrastructure investments yield higher returns in the already-developed eastern regions, human capital investments are more effective in mitigating inequality in less-developed areas (Fleisher et al., 2010). Moreover, globalization, marketization, and decentralization have been identified as key forces shaping China's regional economic trajectories (Li & Wei, 2010). The spatial clustering of industries further exacerbates regional inequality by concentrating wealth and opportunities in specific locations, leaving other regions behind (Fan & Scott, 2003; Wei, 2015). The spatial dimension of regional inequality manifests in factors such as locality, proximity, district characteristics, local context, and neighborhood effects (Wei, 2015).

Beyond China, broader studies on regional disparities in transition economies, such as those within the European Union, reveal the coexistence of divergence and convergence processes. Petrakos et al. (2005) suggest that regional inequalities follow a procyclical pattern, with dynamic regions expanding more rapidly during periods of economic growth and contracting more slowly during downturns. This implies that economic growth alone is insufficient to close regional gaps, necessitating targeted policy interventions (Petrakos, 2001).

Finally, Storper's (2018) research on regional economic polarization introduces an additional perspective by emphasizing the role of institutional and socio-cultural factors in shaping regional inequality. He argues that economic divergence is reinforced by patterns of migration, skill formation, and socialization, creating entrenched disparities. Furthermore, his concept of "separate worlds"

underscores how economic divergence influences political attitudes and social perceptions, contributing to dissatisfaction and the politics of resentment in lagging regions (Storper, 2021).

Green transition constitutes an emerging area of interest within this community, as several studies explore the interplay between green transformation and regional coordinated development in China (Zhao et al., 2023; Xu et al., 2024; Zhuo et al., 2024). Evidence suggests that green transition offers a new developmental paradigm strongly linked to efficiency and sustainability, resulting in a relocation of resources between and within regions (Xu et al., 2024). This shift, followed by human capital investments and deeper policy adjustments, can gradually improve the quality of economic development through resource conservation and environmental improvement, resulting in a mutually beneficial state between geographically proximate regions (Zhuo et al., 2024).

3.4 Community 4: Entrepreneurial ecosystems

This research community highlights that entrepreneurship plays a crucial role in shaping regional development by driving innovation, fostering institutional capacity, and defining the character of place. Entrepreneurs act as agents of change, recognizing opportunities, mobilizing resources, and generating value, which collectively contribute to the vibrancy of regional economies (Feldman, 2014). While traditional approaches to regional development have often overlooked the strategic actions of entrepreneurs, the entrepreneurial ecosystem perspective highlights their central role in creating interdependent networks that facilitate economic growth (Stam, 2015; Acs et al., 2017). Regional variations in entrepreneurship emerge due to factors such as human capital, knowledge spillovers, population growth, and the presence of small firms, all of which interact to shape local economic trajectories (Qian et al., 2013). Rather than relying on deterministic models, successful regional development depends on fostering an environment where entrepreneurship can thrive through supportive policies, institutional frameworks, and public-private collaboration (Fritsch & Mueller, 2008; Qian et al., 2013). By integrating entrepreneurship into regional policy, a shift can occur from focusing on mere firm creation to cultivating a dynamic, innovation-driven regional economy (Stam, 2015).

Another perspective addressed by this research community refers to the investigation of the effects of new business formation on regional development. Emphasis is placed on existing lags between new business entering the market and the effects on it, pointing out that both direct and indirect effects exist (Fritsch & Mueller, 2008; Van Stel & Suddle, 2008). Direct effects include mostly the creation of new jobs, whereas indirect effects refer to aspects of securing efficiency, acceleration of structural change, amplified innovation and innovative entry (Fritsch & Mueller, 2004; Fritsch, 2008). Evidence also suggests that increased levels of new firm formation relate to stimulated economic development due to their ability for fostering innovation and the introduction of new technologies (Baptista et al., 2008).

Finally, the role of social capital to accelerate the impact of entrepreneurship on regional development is another key element explored under this research community. Specifically, different types of social capital, such as bonding, bridging and linking social capital, may indicate diversified impacts on economic development depending on the regional context under which it operates (Malecki, 2012). A balanced place-based synthesis of the different types of social capital is essential to be identified in each case to maximize the benefits resulting from its positive outcomes, such as business reliability and trust (Malecki, 2012).

3.5 Community 5: EU Cohesion Policy

The fifth research community focuses on exploring the ways in which the EU Cohesion Policy has affected regional development perspectives. Built around the equity-efficiency trade-off debate, studies included in this community investigate various factors, such as spillover effects, the type of investments, quality of governance and territorial capital, that may boost or hinder the efficiency of the EU Cohesion Policy (Dall'Erba & Le Gallo, 2008; Rodríguez-Pose & Garcilazo, 2015; Fratesi & Perucca, 2019).

Starting with the spillover effects, they play a crucial role in determining the effectiveness of the EU's Cohesion Policy, as they highlight the interconnected nature of regional development and challenge the assumption that investments solely benefit target regions (Dall'Erba & Le Gallo, 2008; Mohl & Hagen, 2010). The presence of significant spatial spillovers suggests that regional growth is influenced not only by direct investments but also by the economic performance of neighboring regions, implying that omitting spatial effects from evaluations leads to unreliable conclusions (Mohl & Hagen, 2010). Furthermore, the effectiveness of structural funds varies depending on time lags and policy objectives, with Objective 1 funds showing more robust positive impacts compared to Objectives 2 and 3 (Rodríguez-Pose & Fratesi, 2004; Esposti & Bussoletti, 2008; Mohl & Hagen, 2010). This complexity underscores the need for a refined regional policy approach that accounts for spillover dynamics to ensure that Cohesion Policy effectively promotes long-term convergence rather than exacerbating core-periphery divides (Dall'Erba & Le Gallo, 2008; Pellegrini et al., 2013; Gagliardi & Percoco, 2017).

Additionally, the type of investment seems to matter when it comes to prioritization. Empirical studies indicate that structural funds, particularly when allocated to infrastructure, may not always reduce regional inequalities due to industry agglomeration in core regions, as predicted by new economic geography (Rodríguez-Pose & Fratesi, 2004; Dall'Erba & Le Gallo, 2008). While investments in human capital show more consistent positive effects on convergence, transportation infrastructure can inadvertently reinforce spatial disparities by enhancing accessibility benefits in already-developed areas (Rodríguez-Pose & Fratesi, 2004).

Moreover, studies in this field also show that the effectiveness of EU Cohesion Policy in fostering regional growth is significantly influenced by local economic structures and territorial capital. Percoco (2017) highlights that the impact of Structural Funds varies across regions due to differences in economic composition, particularly the relative size of the service sector. While Cohesion Policy has been found to be mildly effective in promoting growth, regions with an overdeveloped service sector tend to experience lower growth rates, suggesting a misallocation of financial resources. This aligns with Baumol's (2001) argument that a shift from manufacturing to services, particularly when driven by public investment, may hinder productivity growth. Conversely, regions with an underdeveloped service sector benefit more from EU funding, as the expansion of services complements other economic sectors and stimulates broader development. Meanwhile, additional evidence emphasizes the role of territorial capital, arguing that the returns on Cohesion Policy investments are higher when they align with a region's existing assets (Fratesi & Perucca, 2019). Regions with well-developed territorial capital experience enhanced policy effectiveness, while those with weaker or unbalanced capital structures may require sustained long-term investment to realize meaningful growth.

Finally, the EU Cohesion Policy has played a crucial role in shaping the governance structure in multiple levels fostering or hindering the effectiveness of regional development investments (Bachtler & McMaster, 2008; Rodríguez-Pose & Garcilazo, 2015). It has been argued that Structural Funds have enhanced the role of regional and local actors in economic development, fostering multilevel governance and stimulating institutional evolution (Bachtler & McMaster, 2008). This increased role

of governance structures has also triggered discussions on the ways in which the quality of governance and existing institutions have also impacted the efficiency of EU Cohesion Policy investments, pointing out that weak institutions hinder the absorption and efficient utilization of funds, reducing their impact on regional growth (Rodríguez-Pose & Garcilazo, 2015).

3.6 Community 6: The rise of the city-regions

The sixth research community covers aspects related to the rise of the city-regions and theoretical perspectives underlying their developmental potential. Together with Community 1, this is the most recently growing research community, as over 55% of the source documents belonging to it have been published after 2020.

City-regions have emerged as dominant economic and spatial entities in the era of globalization, functioning as key engines of regional and global economic development. City-regions are dense, interconnected clusters of capital, labor, and social activity, extending beyond traditional metropolitan boundaries to include surrounding hinterlands (Scott, 2001; Hall & Pein, 2006). These regions thrive on agglomeration economies, where firms and industries benefit from proximity, shared infrastructure, and knowledge spillovers, reinforcing cycles of growth and innovation (Harrison, 2012). Unlike the traditional core-periphery model, city-regions are decentralized and increasingly autonomous, capable of influencing national and global economic landscapes (Scott, 2001; Hall & Pein, 2006). The rise of city-regions is further linked to the decline of the central-state's control over economic governance, as they function as independent hubs for policymaking and planning (Harrison, 2012; Wang & Zheng, 2024).

Regional integration and coordinated development are two central notions that are being analyzed under the prism of expanding city-regions, especially using case studies from China such as the Yangtze River Delta and the Pearl River Delta (Li & Wu, 2013; Li et al., 2022; Wang & Zheng, 2024). City-regions act as key drivers of regional integration by facilitating economic collaboration across urban agglomerations, allowing neighboring cities to transcend administrative boundaries and operate as interconnected networks (Ye et al., 2018). This integration optimizes land use and resource allocation while enhancing industrial cooperation and ecological initiatives (Li & Wu, 2013; Li et al., 2022). However, regional integration is not without challenges. Competition among cities within urban agglomerations often leads to resource misallocation and conflicting policy priorities, which can limit the effectiveness of integration efforts (Xu & Yeh, 2005; Chen et al., 2024). Despite these obstacles, city-regions remain instrumental in shaping spatial strategies that promote sustainable urbanization and economic growth at both national and transnational levels.

At the same time, coordinated development, which is closely linked to regional integration, aims to balance economic expansion while addressing disparities between cities within urban agglomerations. By fostering intercity collaboration and rationalizing the division of labor among large, medium, and small cities, city-regions contribute to industrial specialization and improved regional synergy (Guo & Ma, 2022). In China, policies for coordinated development emphasize the role of urban agglomerations in restructuring economic activities and governance models, particularly to reduce land finance dependency (Chen et al., 2024). However, these policies often produce uneven results, as core cities tend to benefit disproportionately, sometimes at the expense of peripheral areas (Li et al., 2022). This uneven development raises concerns about spatial inequality, highlighting the need for strategic planning and enhanced governance.

3.7 Community 7: Tourism

The seventh research community reveals a core knowledge production around the relationship between tourism and regional development. Tourism has long been recognized as a catalyst for regional development, particularly in peripheral areas where traditional industries are in decline. According to Kauppila et al. (2009), tourism can help address regional disparities by creating employment opportunities and diversifying local economies. In rural areas with high unemployment and aging populations, tourism is often seen as the only industry with significant growth potential. It has also been argued that tourism can act as a wealth transfer mechanism, bringing economic benefits from core urban centers to underdeveloped regions (Saarinen, 2003). Additionally, tourism is not an isolated industry but rather a networked system that connects various economic sectors, such as transportation, hospitality, and retail, amplifying its impact on regional economies (Bellini et al., 2019; Hall & Williams, 2019). However, the effectiveness of tourism as a regional development tool depends on its integration into broader economic and social strategies rather than being pursued solely for profit-driven growth.

Despite the growing recognition of tourism's role in regional development, Calero and Turner (2020) point out that there is a lack of strong theoretical frameworks guiding empirical research in this area. While tourism is widely studied within economic and social contexts, much of the existing literature lacks a structured approach to understanding how tourism contributes to regional transformation. For example, some studies indicate that a tourism boom improves urban welfare, but its effects on rural welfare remain uncertain (Chao et al., 2006). This highlights the need for more robust theoretical models that examine the diverse and sometimes contradictory impacts of tourism on different regions (Calero and Turner, 2020). Without a clear theoretical foundation, policy decisions regarding tourism and regional development risk being based on fragmented or case-specific findings rather than comprehensive, evidence-based strategies.

Moreover, governance plays a crucial role in ensuring that tourism development benefits local communities and aligns with regional economic goals. Stoffelen and Vanneste (2017) argue that tourism should be viewed as a transformative force in regional development rather than an isolated economic sector. Effective governance mechanisms help manage stakeholder interests, ensure equitable distribution of tourism benefits, and address institutional mismatches, especially in cross-border contexts. Additionally, participative management and integrative networking are essential for embedding tourism within local economies and preventing external actors from monopolizing its benefits (Montanari & Staniscia, 2014). Governance also functions as a regulatory mechanism that aligns tourism development with environmental sustainability, social equity, and long-term economic stability. Without strong governmental structures, tourism risks becoming exploitative, reinforcing economic inequalities rather than alleviating them.

3.8 Community 8: Globalized regional development

The final research community identified in this study focuses on the concept of globalized regional development highlighting the evolving relationship between regional economies and the broader global economic system. The concept of globalized regional development has gained prominence as globalization continues to reshape economic geographies (Wei, 2002). MacKinnon et al. (2002) highlight how the increasing globalization of production and finance has weakened national economic coherence, reducing state control over investment flows and exposing regions to heightened international competition. This shift has led to a renewed emphasis on regional intervention as a means

to shape economic development, particularly through fostering learning and innovation as sources of competitive advantage (Hess, 2004). The literature on regional development has transitioned from a focus on agglomeration economies and industrial districts to broader concerns with social and institutional foundations of growth, as seen in concepts like learning regions and innovative milieus (Camagni, 1991; Cooke & Morgan, 1998; Storper, 1997). In this regard, regional development is now understood in relation to global production networks, recognizing that regions are embedded in wider transnational economic structures that shape their developmental trajectories (Yeung, 2013).

The evolution from new regionalism to the globalization of regional development reflects a broader shift in economic geography. Initially, new regionalism emphasized endogenous growth, regional innovation systems, and localized knowledge spillovers (MacLeod, 2001; Moulaert & Sekia, 2003). However, scholars have criticized this perspective for overlooking globalization's role in restructuring regional economies (Wei, 2002; Hadjimichalis, 2006). The transition towards a globalized regional development underscores the significance of inter-regional competition, with regions striving to strategically position themselves within global production networks (Hudson, 2007).

Within this framework, the concepts of global value chains (GVCs), global commodity chains (GCCs), and global production networks (GPNs) provide analytical tools for understanding regional development in a globalized context. The GVC and GCC perspectives emphasize value creation, power structures, and the hierarchical organization of production on a global scale, often downplaying the role of place and local agency (Wei, 2010; Coe et al., 2019). The GPN approach, however, presents a more multi-scalar perspective, acknowledging the strategic coupling between global lead firms and local actors (Yeung, 2013). This actor-specific approach contrasts with earlier dependency models, which viewed regions as passive recipients of external investment. Instead, the GPN framework conceptualizes regional development as a trans-local, dynamic process influenced by both global and local forces (Dicken & Malmberg, 2001; Hess, 2004). The integration of regions into the global economy varies depending on geographical contexts, requiring nuanced analyses that move beyond simplistic global-local dichotomies (Wei, 2010). This perspective suggests that regional policymakers must strategically assess their positioning within GPNs to maximize developmental opportunities, balancing local capabilities with global economic trends.

4. Discussion: Conceptualizing research on regional development during the last 25 years

The previous empirical analysis provided a comprehensive overview of regional development research over the past 25 years. Synthesizing this information is crucial for conceptualizing the key aspects that have shaped and continue to influence this field. Our results indicate that core thematic communities cover four broad areas of interest as indicated in Fig. 4. These communities represent distinct yet interconnected research areas, highlighting various aspects of regional economic and policy dynamics. These include sectoral structure, local actors, governance, and transition processes, all of which collectively shape the evolution of regional development research.

Starting with the sectoral structure as a fundamental element, the adoption of new technologies and developmental paths lies in the heart of this research area. Research into communities C1 (Path dependence and industrial evolution) and C7 (Tourism) can be placed within this component, as their primary focus is to investigate ways in which path dependence and evolution in general, and tourism more specifically, can promote regional development opportunities. Adopting key frameworks that guide regional strategic objectives and operational practices is essential for efficiently integrating

sector-specific dynamics, creating a unified approach that serves as a blueprint for future actions and investments.

Fig. 4. The A4 framework for regional development research.

Building on established sectoral frameworks, local actors—such as academia, public authorities, businesses, and community organizations—adapt these strategies to better align with regional specificities. Research communities C2 (The role of HEIs) and C4 (Entrepreneurial ecosystems) are particularly relevant to this aspect of regional development. This stage highlights the importance of adaptation, as local stakeholders refine broader strategies to address specific needs, resources, and challenges. Ensuring that these frameworks are not only theoretically robust but also practically applicable is essential for fostering more targeted and effective regional development efforts.

Alongside sectoral structures and local adaptations, governance bodies at various levels play a crucial role in applying and executing developed policies and strategies. This includes establishing regulatory frameworks, funding mechanisms, and administrative processes that support and enhance regional development. Research communities C3 (Regional disparities and inequality) and C5 (EU Cohesion Policy) are particularly relevant to this aspect, emphasizing the critical role of governance in ensuring effective policy implementation and bridging the gap between strategy and practice. By facilitating coordinated action, enforcing accountability, and overseeing progress, governance structures help drive sustainable and inclusive regional development.

Finally, the empirical analysis of the literature suggests that transitions—whether driven by economic shifts, technological advancements, or social transformations—play a crucial role within this research-driven framework. Successfully navigating these transitions requires the regional capacity to align diverse structures, actors, and policy frameworks with broader regional and national objectives. This alignment ensures that changes are effectively coordinated, minimizing disruptions while maximizing positive outcomes. Research communities relevant to this component include C6 (Rise of the city-regions) and C8 (Globalized regional development), highlighting the significance of agglomeration and globalization processes in shaping regional development.

Following the abovementioned perspective, the 4As (Adopt-Adjust-Apply-Align) framework has been developed to operationalize the ongoing research on regional development during the last 25 years. This can be used as a conceptual tool to structure and analyze the interplay between all regional elements, including sectoral structures, local actors, governance, and transition processes. The Adopt phase represents the selection and integration of key sectoral frameworks that define regional strategic priorities. The Adjust phase captures the role of local actors in modifying and tailoring these frameworks to better fit regional contexts and unique socio-economic conditions. The Apply phase emphasizes governance mechanisms that facilitate the implementation of policies and strategies, ensuring regulatory coherence and resource allocation. Lastly, the Align phase focuses on managing transitions

by synchronizing regional developments with broader national and global trends, fostering resilience and long-term sustainability.

5. Conclusions

In this study, we have explored the intellectual structure of regional development research through a comprehensive bibliometric analysis, identifying key themes, influential works, and emerging trends within the field. By examining a wide range of publications and constructing a document citation network, we have uncovered the interconnectedness of various research communities, each contributing to the broader understanding of regional development. This final section synthesizes the key findings, discusses their implications for future research, and offers recommendations for how these insights can be utilized by researchers, policymakers, and practitioners to better navigate the complex landscape of regional development.

Starting with the “Path dependence and industrial evolution” research community (C1), it focuses on the evolutionary dynamics of regional economies, emphasizing industrial restructuring, innovation systems, and path dependence. Grounded in Evolutionary Economic Geography, it explores how regions create and transform economic trajectories through knowledge exchange, institutional support, and smart specialization strategies. Recent discussions highlight the role of system-level agency, social innovation, and development traps in shaping regional resilience and long-term growth, particularly in peripheral and rural areas.

Second, the next research community (C2) explores the role of HEIs in driving regional economic, social, and technological advancement by fostering human capital development, knowledge transfer, and innovation. Emphasizing the importance of regional innovation systems and the Triple Helix model, research in this area highlights how universities collaborate with industry and government to shape policies, support technology transfer, and enhance regional competitiveness, with varying impacts depending on local economic structures and institutional contexts.

Third, research in the “regional disparities and inequality” community (C3) focuses on examining both persistent and emerging patterns across different economic contexts, with a particular emphasis on China. Grounded in the New Economic Geography framework, scholars explore the structural and policy-driven factors contributing to regional inequality, including land use, human capital, and globalization. The research highlights the role of geography and industry clustering in regional disparities, as well as the impact of economic cycles on regional divergence. Additionally, an emerging focus on green transition underscores its potential to reshape regional development by promoting sustainability and resource reallocation.

Fourth, the “entrepreneurial ecosystems” research community (C4) explores the pivotal role of entrepreneurship in regional development, emphasizing how entrepreneurs drive innovation, shape institutional capacity, and influence local economic trajectories. This perspective highlights the importance of interdependent networks, social capital, and supportive policy frameworks in fostering entrepreneurship, ultimately shifting the focus from mere business creation to cultivating dynamic, innovation-driven regional economies.

Fifth, the “EU Cohesion Policy” research community (C5) examines the policy’s impact on regional development, focusing on the equity-efficiency trade-off and factors influencing its effectiveness. Key themes include spillover effects, which highlight the interconnected nature of regional growth; the type of investment, where infrastructure and human capital yield differing impacts; territorial capital, which affects policy outcomes based on regional assets; and governance structures, emphasizing how institutional quality and multilevel governance shape policy efficiency. This body of research

underscores the complexity of regional convergence and the need for nuanced, place-based policy approaches.

The sixth research community (C6) focuses on “the rise of city-regions” as dominant economic and spatial entities, analyzing their role in regional integration, coordinated development, and governance shifts. With over 55% of its contributions published after 2020, this rapidly growing research community explores how city-regions transcend traditional metropolitan boundaries, drive economic collaboration, and reshape policy frameworks, particularly through case studies from China’s Yangtze River and Pearl River Deltas.

The “tourism” research community (C7) explores the role of tourism as a catalyst for regional development, particularly in peripheral and rural areas facing economic decline. While tourism has the potential to create jobs, diversify local economies, and act as a wealth transfer mechanism, its effectiveness depends on integration into broader economic and social strategies. However, the field lacks strong theoretical frameworks, leading to fragmented research and uncertain policy implications. Governance is highlighted as a critical factor in ensuring equitable tourism benefits.

The last identified research community (C8) focuses on the concept of “globalized regional development”, examining the evolving relationship between regional economies and the broader global economic system. It emphasizes the influence of globalization on regional economic structures, highlighting the shift from localized growth models to an understanding of regions as interconnected within global production networks, where regions must strategically position themselves within global value chains to maximize development opportunities.

Operationalizing the outcomes of this detailed bibliometric exercise included the development of an operational framework for leveraging the benefits of the identified conceptual structures. Therefore, the 4As framework introduced in this study provides a systematic approach to understanding regional development research, offering a structured way to examine how different thematic areas interact over time. It enables scholars and policymakers to assess past trends, identify gaps, and develop more effective strategies for future regional growth. By linking empirical findings with theoretical advancements, the framework serves as a guide for refining regional policies and enhancing their practical applicability. Conceptualizing research through this lens contributes to a deeper and more nuanced understanding of regional development dynamics, shaping future academic inquiry and policy-making efforts.

This methodological approach has been effective in achieving the proposed research objectives, yet several limitations should be acknowledged, as they present opportunities for future research. First, the study relies on a bibliometric analysis of academic literature, which may have excluded relevant publications outside the selected databases. Different databases retrieve varying sets of publications based on indexing criteria, meaning some relevant studies on regional development may not have been captured. Second, this research focuses primarily on peer-reviewed academic sources, omitting grey literature such as policy reports, government documents, and industry white papers. While this ensures academic rigor, incorporating such materials in future studies could provide a more comprehensive perspective on regional development discourse. Lastly, the classification of research communities, while systematically derived, remains subject to interpretative limitations. The evolving nature of regional development research means that additional thematic clusters may emerge over time, warranting further updates and refinements to the proposed framework. Future studies employing large-scale expert validation or mixed-method approaches could enhance the robustness and applicability of these findings.

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Appendix

Table A.1: Thematic communities' core literature. AR: Journal article; BO: Book; CH: Book chapter; RE: Review; CO: Conference paper.

Thematic Community	Title	Author(s)	Year	Type	In-degree centrality
C1	Path dependence and regional economic	Martin R. Sunley	2006	AR	200

	evolution	P.				
	Related variety unrelated variety and regional economic growth	Frenken K. Van Oort F. Verburg T.	2007	AR	196	
	How do regions diversify over time industry relatedness and the development of new growth paths in regions	Neffke F. Henning M. Boschma R.	2011	AR	106	
	Trinity of change agency regional development paths and opportunity spaces	Grillitsch M. Sotarauta M.	2020	AR	88	
	Smart specialisation opportunities and challenges for regional innovation policy	Foray D.	2014	BO	78	
	Towards a comprehensive understanding of new regional industrial path development	Hassink R. Isaksen A. Trippel M.	2019	AR	76	
	Creating new paths offshore wind policy activism and peripheral region development	Dawley S.	2014	AR	63	
	Industrial development in thin regions trapped in path extension	Isaksen A.	2015	AR	52	
	Exogenously led and policy supported new path development in peripheral regions analytical and synthetic routes	Isaksen A. Trippel M.	2017	AR	49	
	How to unlock regional economies from path dependency from learning region to learning cluster	Hassink R.	2005	AR	48	
C2	Regional development in the knowledge-based economy the construction of advantage	Cooke P. Leydesdorff L.	2006	AR	58	
	Regional innovation systems theory empirics and policy	Asheim B.T. Smith H.L. Oughton C.	2011	AR	52	
	The innovating region toward a theory of knowledge-based regional development	Etzkowitz H. Klofsten M.	2005	AR	48	
	Tiers of engagement by universities in their regions' development	Boucher G. Conway C. Van Der Meer E.	2003	AR	39	
	The role of universities in regional development conceptual models and policy institutions in the UK Sweden and Austria	Trippel M. Sinozic T. Lawton Smith H.	2015	AR	36	
	Universities as key knowledge infrastructures in regional innovation systems	Charles D.	2006	AR	30	
	Universities and territorial development reshaping the regional role of UK universities	Charles D.	2003	RE	27	
	Lessons for the future	Furuseth O.J. Lapping M.B.	2017	CH	25	
	Contributions of universities to regional	Goldstein H.A.	2004	AR	24	

	economic development a quasi-experimental approach	Renault C.S.			
	The economic and innovation contribution of universities a regional perspective	Huggins R. Johnston A.	2009	AR	21
C3	Human capital economic growth and regional inequality in China	Fleisher B.; Li H.; Zhao M.Q.	2010	AR	40
	The spatial-temporal hierarchy of regional inequality of China	Li Y.; Wei Y.H.D.	2010	AR	33
	The new economic geography now middle-aged	Krugman P.	2011	AR	28
	Spatiality of regional inequality	Wei Y.D.	2015	AR	27
	Regional development in China transitional institutions embedded globalization and hybrid economies	Wei Y.H.D.	2007	AR	26
	Separate worlds explaining the current wave of regional economic polarization	Storper M.	2018	AR	26
	Beyond convergence space scale and regional inequality in China	Wei Y.H.D.; Ye X.	2009	AR	24
	Growth integration and regional disparities in the European Union	Petrakos G.; Rodríguez-Pose A.; Rovolis A.	2005	AR	22
	Industrial agglomeration and development a survey of spatial economic issues in east Asia and a statistical analysis of Chinese regions	Fan C.C.; Scott A.J.	2003	AR	21
	Forging ahead and falling behind changing regional inequalities in postreform China	Lu M.; Wang E.	2002	AR	21
C4	Entrepreneurial ecosystems and regional policy a sympathetic critique	Stam E.	2015	AR	75
	Effects of new business formation on regional development over time	Fritsch M.; Mueller P.	2004	AR	56
	The impact of new firm formation on regional development in the Netherlands	Van Stel A.; Suddle K.	2008	AR	35
	Regional systems of entrepreneurship the nexus of human capital knowledge and new firm formation	Qian H.; Acs Z.J.; Stough R.R.	2013	AR	28
	Entrepreneurship regional development and job creation the case of Portugal	Baptista R.; Escária V.; Madruga P.	2008	AR	27
	How does new business formation affect regional development introduction to the special issue	Fritsch M.	2008	AR	24
	Regional social capital why it matters	Malecki E.J.	2012	AR	23
	The effect of new business formation on regional development over time the case of	Fritsch M.; Mueller P.	2008	AR	23

	Germany				
	The lineages of the entrepreneurial ecosystem approach	Acs Z.J.; Stam E.; Audretsch D.B.; O'Connor A.	2017	AR	22
	The character of innovative places entrepreneurial strategy economic development and prosperity	Feldman M.P.	2014	AR	22
C5	Between development and social policies the impact of European structural funds in objective 1 regions	Rodríguez-Pose A.; Fratesi U.	2004	AR	77
	Quality of government and the returns of investment examining the impact of cohesion expenditure in European regions	Rodríguez-Pose A.; Garcilazo E.	2015	AR	39
	Measuring the effects of European regional policy on economic growth a regression discontinuity approach	Pellegrini G.; Terribile F.; Tarola O.; Muccigrosso T.; Busillo F.	2013	AR	34
	Local economic development agglomeration economies and the big push 100 years of evidence from the Tennessee valley authority	Kline P.; Moretti E.	2014	AR	33
	Do EU structural funds promote regional growth new evidence from various panel data approaches	Mohl P.; Hagen T.	2010	AR	31
	The impact of European cohesion policy in urban and rural regions	Gagliardi L.; Percoco M.	2017	AR	30
	Impact of objective 1 funds on regional growth convergence in the European union a panel data approach	Esposti R.; Bussoletti S.	2008	AR	22
	Eu cohesion policy and the role of the regions investigating the influence of structural funds in the new member states	Bachtler J.; McMaster I.	2008	CO	19
	Impact of European cohesion policy on regional growth does local economic structure matter	Percoco M.	2017	AR	17
	Regional convergence and the impact of European structural funds over 1989-1999 a spatial econometric analysis	Dall'erba S.; Le Gallo J.	2008	AR	15
C6	The polycentric metropolis learning from megacity regions in Europe	Hall P.; Pain K.	2012	BO	44
	City profile	Xu J.; Yeh A.G.O.	2003	AR	27
	City repositioning and competitiveness building in regional development new development strategies in Guangzhou China	Xu J.; Yeh A.G.O.	2005	RE	15
	Globalization and the rise of city-regions	Scott A.J.	2001	AR	15

	The emergence of centrally initiated regional plan in China a case study of Yangtze River delta regional plan	Li Y.; Wu F.	2013	AR	14
	Regional cooperation and its role in declining the impact of world crisis over tourism activity in Romania	Sztruten G.; Oprescu A.; Gheorghe C.; Sebea M.	2009	CO	14
	Spatial division of labor	Smith A.	2009	CH	14
	Integrated regional development comparison of urban agglomeration policies in China	Li L.; Ma S.; Zheng Y.; Xiao X.	2022	AR	13
	Regional connectivity	Sokol M.	2009	CH	13
	Life after regions the evolution of city-regionalism in England	Harrison J.	2012	AR	12
C7	Sustainable tourism planning and regional development in peripheries a Nordic view	Kauppila P.; Saarinen J.; Leinonen R.	2009	AR	21
	The regional economics of tourism in northern Finland the socioeconomic implications of recent tourism development and future possibilities for regional development	Saarinen J.	2003	AR	17
	Why some regions will decline a Canadian case study with thoughts on local development strategies	Polèse M.; Shearmur R.	2006	AR	15
	Tourism and innovation	Hall C.M.; Williams A.M.	2019	BO	12
	Tourism and cross-border regional development insights in European contexts	Stoffelen A.; Vanneste D.	2017	AR	11
	Services and regional development	Illeris S.	2009	AR	10
	Regional economic development and tourism a literature review to highlight future directions for regional tourism research	Calero C.; Turner L.W.	2020	AR	10
	Regional development platforms and related variety exploring the changing practices of food tourism in north Jutland Denmark	James L.; Halkier H.	2016	AR	9
	Regional governance and rural development in Germany the implementation of leader	Böcher M.	2008	AR	8
	Tourism and regional economic resilience from a policy perspective lessons from smart specialization strategies in Europe	Bellini N.; Grillo F.; Lazzeri G.; Pasquinelli C.	2017	AR	8
C8	Learning innovation and regional development a critical appraisal of recent debates	Mackinnon D.; Cumbers A.; Chapman K.	2002	AR	71
	Regional development and the competitive	Yeung H.W.	2009	AR	51

dynamics of global production networks an east Asian perspective					
New regionalism reconsidered globalization and the remaking of political economic space	MacLeod G.	2001	AR	49	
Restructuring industrial districts scaling up regional development a study of the Wenzhou model China	Wei Y.D.; Li W.; Wang C.	2007	AR	28	
Regions and regional uneven development forever some reflective comments upon theory and practice	Hudson R.	2007	AR	24	
Spatial relationships towards a reconceptualization of embeddedness	Hess M.	2004	AR	22	
Innovation and urban regions as national and international nodes for the transfer and sharing of knowledge	Simmie J.	2003	AR	20	
Beyond the Sunan model trajectory and underlying factors of development in Kunshan China	Wei Y.D.	2002	AR	20	
Beyond new regionalism beyond global production networks remaking the Sunan model China	Wei Y.H.D.	2010	AR	19	
Multinationals intra-corporate competition and regional development	Phelps N.A.; Fuller C.	2000	AR	19	
